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INFORMATIONAL INFLUENCE ON THE POLITICAL KNOWLEDGE OF CHILDREN IN THE CONTEXT OF THE HYBRID WAR OF RUSSIA AGAINST UKRAINE

In the context of a hybrid war, modern threats to the information security of children living in the temporarily occupied territories are analyzed, and the prospects for their reintegration into the socio-political field of the Ukrainian state are determined. The article reveals the action of the mechanism of aggressive anti-Ukrainian propaganda, conducted since 2014 on all Russian TV channels and retransmitted to the occupied Ukrainian territories, which, through outright lies and a demonstration of disdain for the leaders of the Ukrainian state, undermines their legitimacy in the eyes of the population of these territories, forms an inadequate attitude in the minds of children to reality, destroys national identity.

It is emphasized that the return by Ukraine of control over the temporarily occupied territories is not a short-term prospect, but requires the development of a long-term strategy for the reintegration of these territories. Such a strategy is especially important for children and adolescents, since their political outlook is formed in an information and socio-cultural environment hostile to Ukraine.

Keywords: *child, information warfare, Ukraine, Russia, public opinion, mass media.*

Formulation of the problem. The aggression of the Russian Federation against Ukraine, which began more than 7 years ago, led to the occupation of some districts of Luhansk and Donetsk regions of Ukraine and the proclamation of pseudo-republics «LPR» and «DPR». In fact, Russia has declared a hybrid war against Ukraine. The population of the occupied territories was under the influence of pro-

Russian media, which was constantly hostile to Ukraine. This propaganda causes special damage to children, as the most vulnerable group of the population with an unformed political culture and consciousness. This problem has long-term consequences in terms of reintegration of the occupied territories into the political field of Ukraine.

In 2014, through the «popular uprisings» inspired by the Russians, Russia occupied 44,000 square kilometers, which is 7% of Ukraine's territory, seized the largest cities in the Donetsk and Luhansk regions, the Russian aggression killed 13 thousand people and more than 28 thousand people were wounded, more than 1.8 million people from the Donbas and the Crimea were forced to move to other places of Ukraine [1]. The Ukrainian Crimea was annexed by the Russian Federation, and some regions of Donetsk and Luhansk regions began to be ruled by the Kremlin's puppet regimes – the so-called «Luhansk People's Republic» and «Donetsk People's Republic».

The fate of the people who fell under the rule of pseudo-republics has since ceased to depend on the actions of the Ukrainian government. Children who remained on the territories occupied by Russia were forced to accept their parents' choices and grow in conditions not only of armed confrontation, but also of information warfare. For these children, the problem of information aggression and information security is put forward.

Information warfare is an important component of the hybrid warfare, launched by the Russian Federation against the sovereign Ukraine. Such a form of struggle is a combination of methods and means of influencing the information sphere: from a one-time action of information-psychological and informational and technical influence to a complex of actions that involve planned, systematic influence on the consciousness and behavior of people by spreading biased, incomplete or inaccurate information for the purpose of inclining them to commit actions beneficial to the subject of information influence [2, p. 20–30].

The main object of information attacks is the consciousness of an individual whose hidden influence is exercised through their psyche and nervous system, mainly at the subconscious level, «bypassing conscious control, through the sphere of unconscious, unclear, and unconscious reactions of the human psyche» [3, p. 117]. The age-specificity of a child results in the fact that the hidden influence on their psyche is much larger than that of an adult, and the threats to their information security are more significant and vivid.

Methodology. The general situation in the occupied territories of Donetsk and Luhansk regions is reproduced using the historical retrospective method. Content analysis is used in the study of propaganda products of the Russian Federation on the territories of «LPR»/«DPR» controlled by it. Disclosure of the peculiarities of

media influence on the political consciousness of modern children is carried out by means of analysis of actual sociological research, that is, using sociological methods of questionnaires and interviews. Formulation of conclusions is carried out through the use of the general method of induction.

Analysis of recent research and publications. The problem of informational and psychological confrontation in modern society is studied in the writings by H. Hrachev, O. Drozdov, M. Vilenchyk, N. Matveievf. The problems of forming youth and children's political culture and the influence of the media on this process are studied by A. Valeieva, N. Savina, Yu. Zubok, O. Honcharova, S. Belobanova, L. Shakirova. The peculiarities of the information influence on the child's psyche are considered by A. Bandura, O. Baranov, V. Bryzhko, I. Aristova, E. Erikson, J. Zharkov, M. Prysiazhniuk, N. Savinova, V. Petryk, V. Pylypchuk, K. Bieliakov, A. Fioktistov and other scientists.

At the same time, it should be emphasized that the problem of the negative impact of the information warfare on the child's consciousness and behavior remains underinvestigated today and requires a more thorough study.

The purpose of the article is to determine the forms of manifestation and social consequences of the destructive influence of Russian propaganda on the formation of the political culture of children living in the temporarily occupied territories of Donetsk and Luhansk regions.

Presenting main material. The most noticeable and harmful manifestation of the negative information influence on a person is the destructive information influence. The term «destruction» comes from the Latin «destructio», which in translation means «demolition, collapse». The modern interpretation of the term «destruction» is a violation or breaking of the normal structure of something» [2, p. 23]. Hence, the destructive information influence on the consciousness of the child is a negative influence that causes the violation of the integrity of the individual, the destruction of their mentality and irreversible violations in their psyche, which makes it impossible for the formation of a person to be normal.

Of course, propaganda is the main tool of destructive information influence. The essence of propaganda is the manipulation of consciousness, to achieve the goal it needs to cause certain emotions in humans, and its main function is to create a fictitious, parallel reality [4, p. 255].

The aggressive anti-Ukrainian propaganda is currently being conducted on all Russian TV channels and retransmitted to the occupied Ukrainian territories. Examples of such propaganda aimed at the children's audience in the east of the country are the cartoon «Once our life has changed» on the Russian television channel «Smile of a Child», which allegedly was created by refugee children from the Donbas. This fake product shows how the Ukrainian army allegedly bombards

their hometowns by aviation means [5], the New Year's children's fairy tale «Saved Christmas», released on the official channel of «DPR» [6], illustrated children's magazine «Polite Little People», which was distributed in the city of Luhansk [7]. An outright lie, a disdainful attitude towards the leaders of the Ukrainian state undermine their legitimacy, form an inadequate attitude towards reality in the child's mind, undermine national identity, and form a fierce attitude toward the Ukrainian Armed Forces as «invaders», but not defenders of the Motherland. The content of what is going on in Luhansk and Donetsk regions is disturbed: Russian invaders are presented as «liberators», and on the contrary, Ukrainian liberators are presented as «invaders». Although the territory of the occupied regions of Donetsk and Luhansk regions is in fact Ukrainian ethnic lands dominated by representatives of the Ukrainian people (although in a lesser proportion than in other regions of Ukraine, with the exception of the Crimean autonomy, where ethnic Russians are dominant). Hence, there are no objective grounds for any autonomy in Ukraine in the Donbas and can not be. All the specifics of this region is that, because of its geographical proximity to Russia, it has always been in a foreign information field and has formed a specific semi-Soviet consciousness and regional patriotism, which is not entirely consistent with Ukrainian identity. But this is a significant failure of the Ukrainian state, which allowed to violate its information sovereignty, which eventually led to the violation of our territorial sovereignty through the foreign occupation of the Russian Federation. As a result, a generation of ethnic Ukrainians is formed in the occupied and adjoining territories, and they are deprived of national identity, are not tangent to their national culture and language, and do not perceive Ukraine positively as their own Motherland. This is the problem that will have to be solved for decades. Moreover, the contemporary political culture of the Ukrainian people is fragmentary, it is not monolithic, since it lacks the established components, and many of those established have not been formed yet. It should be emphasized that a large number of political and cultural elements of contemporary Ukrainians do not correspond to the traditions of the Ukrainian nation and our national character [8, p. 175]. Now, Ukrainians must finally abandon all archaic, outdated post-colonial mental guides and restore the best national traits: democracy, communist centrism, activism-type individualism, tolerance, the cult of honest work, the negation of any authoritarian practices, etc. [9, p. 228–229].

The problem of information security of children in non-controlled areas of Ukraine in «LPR»/«DPR» has a humanitarian and socio-political aspect.

The notion of «media» configures us to the facts that: the life of children passes not only in the real world but also in an artificially established virtual world in which communication is mediated by electronic means of information (mass media); children are under the influence of large volumes of fragmented, mainly audio-visual

information, which has a predominance of the affective component over cognitive, which entails a special kind of assimilation of information messages; in the field of similar, identical informational influence, a large number of people are exposed at once, because the media environment is characterized by a massive impact on large audiences, which are segmented into a large number of target groups.

Information space influence on the child is sometimes crucial to the formation of the future personality. The level of consciousness, moral upbringing of a person is determined by their ability to appreciate the highest values – sincerity, kindness and humanity. So what personality values prevail today and what factors influence their formation? Today, one of the main factors is mass media. What is the information space around us filled with?

Today, certain indicators that give grounds to determine the media environment in «LPR»/ «DPR» as aggressive and inhumane have been established. These are their features: 1) excessive volume in the information field of violence, aggression, brutality (media violence); 2) an extremely high manipulative component, which manifests itself in an attempt to make permanent psychological pressure on the worldview, the feeling and behavior of not only consumers of the information product, but also those who are close to them in some social networks, contact groups; 3) artificial instability and turbulence, which contribute to the general feeling of insecurity, and thus, cause frustration, fear, uncertainty in the future, and so on.

For the total influence on the mass consciousness of the inhabitants of the occupied Russian Federation of Ukrainian territories, traditional mass media are used: television, radio, press, books, carriers of outdoor advertising, etc. Moreover, we must pay tribute to the Russians who have high qualifications in conducting information campaigns, operations and in general, in conducting an information warfare.

At the present stage, it is necessary to state in the overwhelming majority of children in the occupied territories the spread of media dependence, weak opposition to the imposition of low-quality media production, immoral values, vulnerability to media manipulations, inability to distinguish fake news from the real ones, low media culture and political culture in general .

Negative influence of mass media on the consciousness of children. The influence of television should be mentioned separately in this context. Despite the prohibition of up to 10 pm, broadcast on TV is filled with action movies with scenes of bloodshed, fights, violence, and the favorite movie heroes of the masses are the bone breakers. Cruelty becomes a stereotype of our time, and modesty is a vice. Horror films have become an interesting entertainment, even for children, where the «heroes» are disgusting monsters. The lack of elementary etiquette is dominated

in the cinema rental. The audience laugh at the rude comedians, where one has to have fun, when a person falls, suffers and gets into stressful situations.

Here, we should emphasize the negative impact of television and cinema on the physiology of children. This includes: forced immobility, impaired motor development, deficiency in the formation of brain functions, speech impairment and violations in the adequate perception of the world. To the abnormal consequences of excessive exposure of TV on the health of the child should be attributed to: standstill accommodation (movements) of the eyes, hypnotic state of hibernation, influence on the metabolism, narrowing the sight to 6–7 degrees, inhibition in the formation of individual will and independence, failure in the formation of originaive and creative abilities.

There is a depression of the natural children activity. Experiences for characters, even bright and emotionally rich, do not require any actual action, unlike real life, where emotion is necessarily realized in action. Desire departed from the action can undermine future motivation, suppress the natural activity of the child.

There may be underdevelopment of speech. Children begin to speak later, speak reluctantly, the vocabulary is poor and primitive. Mastering the language at an early age occurs only in live direct communication with other people. If the words are not addressed personally and do not require an answer, it does not contribute to the development of language skills.

The extremely negative effect of TV is the ability failure to concentrate attention. Most often this is manifested when a child goes to school. They cannot concentrate on one thing for more than 3–5 minutes; it is difficult for them to sit in a classroom; they need to move. There is an endless kaleidoscope of pictures, music, cluttered phrases on the screen. Frame rate does not make it possible to understand what they see. The child lacks imagination. They lose the ability and desire to do something. They are bored to draw, to design or to invent game plots. The kid is accustomed to passive perception of information. And in real life they wait for someone to do something fun and interesting for them. Submitted not from the voice of a loved person (that is, without synchronization of rhythms in a single energy information system), alienated on-screen visual images can inhibit the child's own fantasies, and, therefore, the basis of their creative activity.

Children often fail to communicate with peers. It is difficult for children to engage in effective communication with friends. It's easier for a small person to press a button and wait for new entertainment than to establish communication with others. At best, children simply push each other while playing.

Aggressiveness as a routine behavioral pattern appears. According to various sociological studies, 60% of children are not afraid of their own or of somebody else's death, they consider «take-down» as normal standard of life, as well as the

fight, revealing episodic attacks of cruelty. Children do not have the ability to think critically since birth, it is formed for a long period of time, with experience and the formation of personality. Everything around is perceived as a rule! Scientists have found that only 50% of parents try to explain to the child the negative aspects of violence shown on television, and 40% do not mind the content of the programs that their children watch. The influence of television on children of all ages is unequal. Up to 2 years old children do not need to watch TV at all, since it interferes with healthy psycho-physiological development. Artificial inhibition of the child's physical activity at an early age can lead to long-term negative psychological consequences. After 3 years, when the child is interested in peers as partners for joint games, the lack of contact with TV can make the child very different from the general public and worsen their socialization.

Famous Canadian psychologist A. Bandura, along with his colleagues, conducted the first studies related to the influence of the media on human behavior. Children from 3 to 7 years old participated in these studies. They were shown short-cut cartoons in which an adult negatively communicated with a doll called Bobbo. After viewing these scenes, the children were given time to play within 10–20 minutes, and the researcher at this time focused attention on each child, fixing their actions and deeds. According to the results of this experiment, it was found that some of the children repeated the behavior of the actor, that is, simulated the acts of aggression [10, p. 321].

According to statistics, boys and girls from 4 to 10 years old watch TV for about 2.5 hours a day; from 11 to 14 years old – for 3 hours a day. Children over 15 years old watch TV for 4 hours a day. From this age, girls spend half an hour more on watching TV than boys. American psychologists estimate: teenagers under twelve years old witness 100,000 scenes of violence and killing on TV [11].

Psychological studies have shown that in our time, 25% of children at the age of four suffer from linguistic developmental disorder. For comparison, in the mid 70's of the XX century language deficit was observed in 4% of children of the same age [12].

Scientists from the American Medical Association conducted research on the impact of the media on child development. During the years of schooling, children see 8,000 murders and 100,000 acts of violence on TV. Researchers concluded that some television programs spread obscenity and debauchery: in 91% of episodes that show sexual intercourse and partners are not married [13].

After watching such programs and films, the child cannot separate virtual reality from real world, and perceives this behavior as a plan for imitation, resulting in the formation of a cruel style of thinking and negation of family values. Sociological research suggests that 58% of young people seek to emulate the behavior of actors,

mostly from foreign films, and 37.3% of adolescents are ready to commit illegal actions based on their actions and deeds [14, p. 51].

Information on TV has a great power of suggestion. If adults are able to bridge the real and virtual world of advertising, children are not able to do this. So gradually the child becomes accustomed to violence and learns to reproduce it in a calm and sustaining way.

In addition to the psychological impact of the media on the child there is also a threat to their physical health. Radiation coming out of the screen, flashing bright spots, frequent image changes influence on the unstable organism of a child. Radiation has an accumulation character, which has a predominant effect on the immune system [15, p. 175].

Ophthalmologists assert that up to eight years old, a complete formation of the eye lens occurs, and by this age the child is contraindicated to look at the TV screen. When watching television programs, human eyes make imperceptible jumps, so-called saccades. The norm is assumed to be from 2 to 5 saccades per second. The number of saccades when the eyes of a human are exposed to TV is sharply reduced [17].

E. Erikson identified eight human formation crises. According to his researches, the most important qualities in the personality are established during the period of childhood, when the basis of a future person is put. The first stages are due solely to the communication of adults with a child, especially mother. After that, the main thing is the relationship in the family and father and mother's attitude in relation to the child. Then the role of education and work for the child's mental development increases [16].

Adolescents check their limitations, seek risky and addictive behavior. Watching movies with violence gives them an opportunity to conditionally meet their needs in acute sensations, to experience excitement, to feel «adrenaline». This need is imposed by the influence of peers, which also reaches its peak in adolescence. Young people often have some sense of competition in the group when watching movies with violence, which encourages them to continue watching. However, adolescents tend to overestimate themselves when checking their own limits and often remain scared after watching especially impressive horror movies that are too hard to watch even for adults. It is assumed that older teens and adults who do not like such films should be given the opportunity to take responsibility for the decision to watch or not watch them. It is for this purpose that the appropriate tags are used, which are often ignored by the owners of the television networks. Thus, scientists in the field of psychology are concerned that we can receive a generation of unmanaged, aggressive and cruel people with a deformed psyche in the near future [18]. An important role in this deformation of the child's mind is played by the

media. The unstable or unformed psyche of the child is often not ready to withstand an information attack.

Conclusions. First, the information warfare is a determining factor in the hybrid war led by the Russian Federation against Ukraine. The essence of the information warfare is to create a set of ways to influence the information industry of the occupied territories in order to systematically influence the political consciousness of local residents through the shattering of false information aimed at justifying their criminal acts.

Second, the main object of informational attacks are children, because their age-specifics (the lack of formation of the worldview and political culture) causes a significant increase in the hidden and explicit influence of information technology on their consciousness and psyche.

Third, the mass media of the Russian Federation carry out a permanent destructive informational and propagandistic influence on the consciousness of children in the occupied Ukrainian territories, which causes an individual integrity disorder, the destruction of their mentality and national consciousness.

Fourth, traditional mass media are used for the total influence on the mass consciousness of the inhabitants of the Ukrainian territories occupied by the Russian Federation, they are television, radio, press, books, carriers of outdoor advertising, etc.

Fifth, most children in the so-called «LPR»/«DPR» have a high media dependence, commitment to low-quality media production, inability to resist mass media manipulation, unconscious commitment to immoral propaganda imposed, extremely low media culture and political culture in general.

Sixth, the media have a detrimental effect, both on the psyche of children and on their physical health, as a means of manipulation, as well as a way to develop aggression. Therefore, in order to avoid the deformation of the psyche in children, it is necessary to adhere to the established norms and rules that restrict the viewing of television programs.

Seventh, the return of Ukraine's control over the temporarily occupied territories is not a short-term prospect, but now Ukrainian authorities have to develop a strategy for the reintegration of these territories and citizens living there. This is especially true for children and adolescents, since they are forced to shape their political outlook in an informative and socio-cultural environment hostile to Ukraine. The consequences of this process may not be predictable and most likely they may be negative.

Recommendations. In connection with this, general recommendations can be made to neutralize the negative influence of modern media on children's consciousness, which any educator can use, and recommendations for the Ukrainian

state regarding the influence on the consciousness of the inhabitants of the occupied territories with a view to their reintegration into the Motherland.

Recommendations to neutralize the negative impact of the media on children

1. It is necessary to develop media education as an extremely important and relevant area of education. The main direction of media education is to integrate experience and build resource attitudes towards the media. Young boys – senior pupils need to be treated as future parents who can take responsibility not only for their lives, but for a new life.

2. It is necessary to form a psychologically-comfortable «educational» environment in the family on the basis of a trusting, tolerant interpersonal interaction of parents and students. This is the most important condition for the development of a positive state of health of a child, the acquisition of moral values.

3. It is necessary to develop students' passion for media information that satisfies the cognitive interests, abilities, moral values of students, helps to neutralize their attention and excessive attraction to plots of violence on the television screen or other mass media.

4. In order to neutralize the negative influence of the mass media on the behavior of children, the development of their critical attitude toward media, educators should be aware of the reasons and motives of their admiration for the subject of violence prevailing in media information and other information products.

5. It is necessary to establish immunity of children against various aggression models, depicted in the media, neutralizing their negative impact on the person.

6. In the event that children exhibit excessive attachment to films, television programs with violence, parents should watch these media products together with their children and direct their attention and experiences on the main ideas of content, positive moral actions, social values disclosed on the screen and beyond.

7. It is necessary to accustom children to creativity, develop critical thinking in them. This will encourage them to be careful, cautious and critical of the media and the products they produce.

For the Ukrainian state it is necessary to restore the influence on the consciousness of the inhabitants of the occupied territories with a view to their reintegration into the Motherland and to do the following: establish special PR-programs for children to form a positive image of the reformed political system of Ukraine; introduce educational programs to explain to voters their rights, electoral procedures, election systems, etc. by the state through educational media; establish a long-term wide-ranging PR-program «We are the Ukrainians!» aimed at forming a patriotic outlook with the participation of well-known sports and pop stars, leaders of public opinion; promote political socialization of citizens through their involvement in political life of the state (membership in political parties, public-

political associations, participation in elections, referendums, meetings, etc.); use national democratic traditions, ideals and values in political PR projects; revive domestic film production and produce a series of films about the historical and contemporary heroes of Ukraine; involve mass media in order to influence the legal consciousness and legal culture of Ukrainian society through the introduction of educational television and radio programs [19, p. 264]; introduce systematic programs for the development of national culture using social advertising and other modern technologies of influence on the mass consciousness [20, p. 374].

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ІНФОРМАЦІЙНИЙ ВПЛИВ НА ПОЛІТИЧНІ ЗНАННЯ ДІТЕЙ У КОНТЕКСТІ ГІБРИДНОЇ ВІЙНИ РОСІЇ ПРОТИ УКРАЇНИ

Постановка проблеми. Агресія Російської Федерації проти України, яка почалася понад 7 років тому, спричинила окупацію деяких районів Луганської та Донецької областей України та оголошення псевдореспублік «ЛНР» та «ДНР». Фактично Росією була оголошена гібридна війна проти України. Населення окупованих територій опинилося під впливом постійної ворожої щодо України пропаганди проросійських ЗМІ. Особливої шкоди ця пропаганда завдає дітям як найбільш вразливій групі населення з неформованою політичною культурою та свідомістю. Ця проблема має довготривалі наслідки у перспективі реінтеграції окупованих територій в політичне поле України.

Аналіз останніх досліджень і публікацій. Проблема інформаційного та психологічного протистояння в сучасному суспільстві досліджується в працях Х. Грачова, О. Дроздова, М. Виленчик, Н. Матвєєва. Проблеми формування молодіжної та

дитячої політичної культури і вплив ЗМІ на цей процес досліджують А. Валєєва, Н. Савіна, Ю. Зубок, О. Гончарова, С. Белобанова, Л. Шакірова. Особливості інформаційного впливу на дитячу психіку розглядають А. Бандура, О. Баранов, В. Брижко, І. Арістова, Е. Еріксон, Я. Жарков, М. Присяжнюк, Н. Савінова, В. Петрик, В. Пилипчук, К. Беляков, А. Фиоктистов та інші вчені.

Мета статті – визначити форми прояву та соціальні наслідки деструктивного впливу російської пропаганди на формування політичної культури дітей, що проживають на тимчасово окупованих територіях Донецької та Луганської областей.

Вклад основного матеріалу. У контексті гібридної війни аналізуються сучасні загрози інформаційної безпеки дітей, які проживають на тимчасово окупованих територіях, і визначаються перспективи їхньої реінтеграції в суспільно-політичне поле української держави. Розкривається дія механізму агресивної антиукраїнської пропаганди, що ведеться з 2014 р. на всіх російських телеканалах і ретранслюється на окуповані українські території,

Висновок. Інформаційна війна є визначальним фактором у гібридній війні, яку веде Російська Федерація проти України. Суть інформаційної війни полягає в створенні комплексу способів впливу на інформаційну індустрію окупованих територій з метою систематичного впливу на політичну свідомість місцевих жителів шляхом роповсюдження неправдивої інформації, спрямованої на виправдання своїх злочинних дій.

Ключові слова: діти, інформаційна війна, Україна, Росія, громадська думка, ЗМІ.

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ИНФОРМАЦИОННОЕ ВЛИЯНИЕ НА ПОЛИТИЧЕСКИЕ ЗНАНИЯ ДЕТЕЙ В КОНТЕКСТЕ ГИБРИДНОЙ ВОЙНЫ РОССИИ ПРОТИВ УКРАИНЫ

В контексте гибридной войны анализируются современные угрозы информационной безопасности детей, проживающих на временно оккупированных территориях, и определяются перспективы их реинтеграции в общественно-политическое поле украинского государства. Раскрывается действие механизма агрессивной антиукраинской пропаганды, ведущейся с 2014 г. на всех российских телеканалах и ретранслирующей на оккупированные украинские территории, которая посредством откровенной лжи и демонстрации пренебрежительного отношения к лидерам

украинского государства подрывает их легитимность в глазах населения этих территорий, формирует в сознании детей неадекватное отношение к действительности, разрушает национальную идентичность.

Подчеркивается, что возвращение Украиной контроля над временно оккупированными территориями не является краткосрочной перспективой, а требует разработки долговременной стратегии реинтеграции этих территорий. Особенно важна такая стратегия для детей и подростков, поскольку их политическое мировоззрение формируется во враждебной Украине информационной и социокультурной среде.

Ключевые слова: дети, информационная война, Украина, Российская Федерация, общественное мнение, СМИ.

